

Sensitivity-representativity-transposition framework application to ^{235}U fast research reactors and MOX assembly designs

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ABSTRACT

The correlation between experiments and target applications can be used to judge the relevance of such experiments and to guide the design of new experiments towards more informative configurations. Such correlations can also be used to quantitatively transfer information from the measured response to any similar target system through nuclear data assimilation and transposition. We present an application of this framework to the latest configuration of the VENUS-F fast reactor, considering several uranium-fueled research reactors (the VENUS-F previous configuration, SNEAK and CEFR). We also introduce the 3D design of the VENUS-F MOX fuel assembly representative of those of MYRRHA and ALFRED foreseen for loading.

Keywords: VENUS-F, representativity, transposition, GLS, nuclear data assimilation

1. INTRODUCTION

Research reactors are crucial milestones orienting research towards innovative reactor designs, to test experimental methods in a reduced scale. To judge how informative an experiment is to an application, the Pearson's correlation (also called representativity or c_k factor) between the two is customarily used. Approaches to experiment design even propose considering it as a guiding figure of merit, rather than an a-posteriori measure of experiment relevance [1]. This is particularly true for fast reactors, where the limited operational experience and the many nuclear data needs can largely be supported by research reactors.

We present a correlation study of reactor integral parameters (k_{eff} and β_{eff}) across several ^{235}U -fueled and MOX-fueled fast systems highlighting pitfalls and difficulties in a complete correlation characterization coming from limitations in the nuclear data uncertainty evaluations. In the context of experiment design, we present a 3D MOX assembly for the VENUS-F reactor, showing the benefit this would bring in terms of correlation with other MOX systems. Finally, to show the overall impact of representative experiments we present the results of transposition [1], an extension of linear data assimilation, from several ^{235}U -fueled reactors to the latest VENUS-F core configuration.

2. MODELS AND METHODS

2.1. Methods

The sensitivity module of Serpent 2.2.0 [2] was used to calculate energy-dependent sensitivity profiles S_x^y scored over the ECCO-33 group structure [3] defined as:

$$S_x^y(E_i) = \frac{\partial y}{\partial x(E_i)} \frac{x(E_i)}{y} \quad \forall \text{igroup: } E_i \in \text{ECCO-33}, \quad (1)$$

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where derivatives of any reactor response y (k_{eff} and β_{eff} in this study) are taken with respect to simulation input data x (in this work: capture, fission, elastic and inelastic scattering cross sections, prompt fission neutron spectrum χ and average neutron multiplicity $\bar{\nu}$ — prompt p and delayed d — of natural isotopes of Pb, Bi, Al, O, C, and ^{56}Fe , ^{235}U and ^{238}U). The nuclear data uncertainty u is propagated to the response uncertainty according to the standard momentum propagation equation:

$$\frac{u(y)}{y} = \sqrt{S_x^y \Sigma S_x^{yT}}, \quad (2)$$

where S_x^y denotes the sensitivity vector to the perturbed nuclides, reactions and energies, Σ is the nuclear data relative covariance matrix associated with the same perturbations and T indicates vector transposition.

Let now J_x^y be the sensitivity vector of y to x computed in a different (target) system. The Pearson's correlation of response y in the two systems induced by the use of the same nuclear data in their modeling is calculated as

$$\rho_x^y(s, j) = \frac{S_x^y \Sigma J_x^{yT}}{\sqrt{S_x^y \Sigma S_x^{yT} \cdot J_x^y \Sigma J_x^{yT}}}, \quad (3)$$

where s and j denote the systems with associated S and J sensitivities. To compute uncertainties and correlations, we consider all available covariance data and null sensitivity when a nuclide is not present in a system, for impurities and alloying elements.

Let us now consider the results of Bayesian inference of any piece of nuclear data σ with relative covariance matrix Σ [4] in system s . The GLLS posterior quantities σ' and Σ' are computed as

$$\frac{\sigma' - \sigma}{\sigma} = \Sigma S^T \left[S \Sigma S^T + M \right]^{-1} \frac{E - y_s}{y_s} \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma' = \Sigma - \Sigma S^T \left[S \Sigma S^T + M \right]^{-1} S \Sigma, \quad (5)$$

where the x, y dependence of S is neglected for the sake of notation, highlighting that these same equations hold for a sensitivity matrix, E indicates the experimental value(s), M the experiment and model relative covariance matrix (scalar in the case of a single experiment) and y_s the corresponding calculated values. The transposition framework [1] yields the posterior calculation value for an application j if nuclear data assimilation performed on s were used to calculate it. Assuming linearity, the posterior target model response $y'_j = y_j + J \frac{\sigma' - \sigma}{\sigma} y_j$ and considering equation 2, y'_j and $u(y'_j)^2$ can be expressed as functions of the representativity as

$$y'_j = y_j + J \Sigma S^T \left[S \Sigma S^T + M \right]^{-1} \frac{E - y_s}{y_s} y_j = y_j + \frac{\rho(s, j)}{1 + \frac{M}{S \Sigma S^T}} \frac{u(y_j)}{u(y_s)} (E - y_s) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{u(y'_j)^2}{y_j'^2} = J \Sigma' J^T = J \Sigma J^T - J \Sigma S^T \left[S \Sigma S^T + M \right]^{-1} S \Sigma J^T = \frac{u(y_j)^2}{y_j^2} \left(1 - \frac{\rho(s, j)^2}{1 + \frac{M}{S \Sigma S^T}} \right), \quad \text{if } J \approx J'. \quad (7)$$

It was shown that sensitivity profiles computed for VENUS-F with different libraries do not exhibit significant differences [5], which should hold even the more for an updated library, supporting the assumption that $J \approx J'$. Considering equation 6, the sign of the update $y'_j - y_j$ is determined by $(E - y_s)$, as all other contributions are positive. Considering a highly correlated case $\rho \approx 1 \implies u(y_j) \approx u(y_s)$ and that generally $M \ll S \Sigma S^T$, $y'_j - y_j = \rho(E - y_s)$. On the other hand, following similar considerations for equation 7, it emerges that the variance reduction is determined by a factor $(1 - \rho^2)$. Hence the impact of ρ is larger on the posterior variance than on its central value.

2.2. Nuclear data

Nuclear data from JEFF-3.3 [6] were processed with SANDY [7], which wraps the NJOY [8] ERRORR and GROUPE modules. NJOY preserves the reaction rate uncertainty when regrouping the evaluated covariance matrix. The group-wise reaction rate calculation does not affect the output covariance matrix structure (chosen to be ECCO-33), but it impacts its values. A finer grid (SCALE-238 [9]) was then used to group the reaction cross sections before folding them with the fast spectrum weighting implemented in NJOY ($iwt=8$). A similar approach was considered for ν , while ECCO-33 was used for both GROUPE and ERRORR processing of χ , for reasons shown in [10]. As any other library, JEFF-3.3 does not provide a complete set of covariance data: among the missing information that of $\bar{\nu}_d$ is relevant for considerations on β_{eff} . The relative covariance matrix of $\bar{\nu}_p$ for $\bar{\nu}_d$ was used for ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu .

2.3. Models

Four ^{235}U -fueled critical research reactor configurations (SNEAK-4A [11], CEFR beginning of life [12] and VENUS-F CC13 [13] and CC14 [14]) and three MOX-fueled reactor assemblies (ALFRED BoL [15], MYRRHA BoL [16] and the MOX assembly designed for VENUS-F [17]) are considered. Each design was modeled in Serpent using JEFF-3.3 nuclear data. 6×10^9 particles and 15 latent generations were used to simulate the ^{235}U systems (full cores), while 10^{10} particles and 10 latent generations were used for the MOX ones (fuel assemblies). This is sufficient to achieve neat convergence of the sensitivities of k_{eff} , while those of β_{eff} are still problematic, especially for scattering reactions, as discussed in section 3.2.

SNEAK is a zero power fast reactor with sodium coolant simulator. In its configuration 4A, the active core consisted of an alternation of sodium alloy plates with metallic uranium fuel of different enrichment (20% and 35% w.t.) and depleted UO_2 . CEFR is a 65 MWth pool-type, sodium-cooled, fast reactor fueled by 64.18% w.t. enriched UO_2 in annular pellets. Above and below the active fuel, a depleted uranium blanket is included. VENUS-F is a fast zero power reactor fueled with 30% w.t. enriched metallic U. Solid components (Pb and Bi) are included in the core lattice and constitute the reactor reflector to simulate heavy-metal-cooled fast reactor designs. VENUS-F CC13 and CC14 also feature graphite reflector assemblies in the core lattice. Figure 1 (a and b) shows the k_{eff} sensitivity to the most relevant reactions in ^{235}U and ^{238}U computed for these four systems (the two configurations of VENUS-F have very similar sensitivities).

The MOX assembly designed for VENUS-F features 14% w.t. PWR-type MOX with lead and bismuth coolant simulators and a central experimental channel, extending previous 2D designs [17, 5]. To establish a fair comparison, the assembly designs of MYRRHA (30%w.t. MOX with LBE coolant) and ALFRED (20.5% w.t. MOX with Pb coolant) are considered. All assembly models feature reflective boundary conditions. Figure 1 (c and d) shows the k_{eff} sensitivity to the most relevant reactions of ^{239}Pu and ^{238}U computed for these three systems. We refer to effective parameters (e.g., k_{eff} rather than k_{∞}) for the assembly models in the following for simplicity of nomenclature.

3. RESULTS

Confidence intervals are reported for uncertainties and correlations. They are computed perturbing each sensitivity profile by a factor $1 \pm f$, where f is the standard error of the Serpent sensitivity calculation bin by bin. Larger confidence intervals are reported for quantities associated with β_{eff} than k_{eff} because of the slower convergence of the β_{eff} sensitivity calculation. A more rigorous uncertainty propagation is deemed not necessary; in any case, Serpent does not output any covariance matrix for the calculated sensitivity.

Figure 1. Left: main k_{eff} sensitivity [%/%] profiles of the considered systems. Right: VENUS-F 3D MOX assembly design: Pb (blue), Bi (yellow), 14 w.t.% MOX (pink), depleted U (green), structures (gray), air (white).

3.1. Uncertainty

Table I reports the calculated k_{eff} and β_{eff} results and their nuclear data uncertainty, propagated with equation 2. The calculated results reflect the difference between full core and single assembly models, with $k_{\text{eff}} \gg 1$ in the latter case. The lower k_{eff} calculated in ALFRED and VENUS-F MOX than in MYRRHA is consistent with the different enrichment of the systems. In the critical ^{235}U -fueled configurations, the large $u(k_{\text{eff}})$ covers for the discrepancy between the calculated k_{eff} and 1, measured in these research reactors. For systems sharing the same fuel, the calculated β_{eff} are rather close to one another, as one would expect. The lower β_{eff} calculated in CEFR results from its higher enrichment. The β_{eff} uncertainty $u(\beta_{\text{eff}}) < 1\%$ reflects the evaluated uncertainty of $\bar{\nu}_p$ (about 0.5%).

Table I. Nuclear data uncertainty propagated to k_{eff} and β_{eff} . JEFF- ν_d indicates addition of $\bar{\nu}_d$ covariance data to JEFF-3.3 and \pm identifies the confidence interval computed as discussed in section 3.

	k_{eff} [-]	$u(k_{\text{eff}})$ [pcm]		β_{eff} [pcm]	$u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$ [pcm]	
	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3- ν_d	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3- ν_d
VENUS-F CC14	1.00291	1489 \pm 5	1489 \pm 5	734	4.6 \pm 0.6	5.7 \pm 0.4
VENUS-F CC13	1.00339	1506 \pm 16	1506 \pm 16	736	5.5 \pm 1.6	6.5 \pm 1.4
SNEAK 4A	1.00079	1694 \pm 12	1694 \pm 12	739	5.3 \pm 1.6	6.4 \pm 1.3
CEFR	0.99901	1562 \pm 5	1562 \pm 5	714	4.8 \pm 0.5	6.0 \pm 0.4
VENUS-F MOX	1.08893	1038 \pm 2	1038 \pm 2	363	2.3 \pm 0.0	2.7 \pm 0.0
MYRRHA (assembly)	1.35084	1001 \pm 1	1001 \pm 1	318	1.8 \pm 0.0	2.2 \pm 0.0
ALFRED (assembly)	1.11920	879 \pm 2	879 \pm 2	343	2.5 \pm 0.0	2.9 \pm 0.0

In ^{235}U systems, $u(k_{\text{eff}})$ is strongly driven by ^{235}U data uncertainties, with (n,f), (n, γ) and the associated covariance being the most relevant contribution, followed by $\bar{\nu}_p$, χ_p and the covariance between (n,f) and (n,el). In the VENUS-F MOX assembly, the 14% enrichment explains the larger $u(k_{\text{eff}})$, as $u(k_{\text{eff}})$ is

driven by capture and scattering in ^{238}U ($\approx 10\%$ of the total variance each), with a lower contribution of $^{239,240}\text{Pu}(n,f)$ and $\bar{\nu}_p$. In the MYRRHA and ALFRED assemblies, $^{240}\text{Pu}(n,f)$ and its correlation with (n,γ) account for the largest share of k_{eff} uncertainty. This is explained by the large evaluated uncertainty around 1 MeV ($\approx 10\%$ vs $\approx 0.5\%$ of $^{239}\text{Pu}(n,f)$). ^{239}Pu and ^{238}U data follow for both systems, with ^{238}U data being overall more relevant in ALFRED as expected from the enrichment difference.

For $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$ in ^{235}U systems, ^{235}U $\bar{\nu}_p$, (n,f) and (n,γ) are the most important uncertainty sources. Elastic scattering in ^{238}U (VENUS-F) and ^{56}Fe (SNEAK) can also be relevant, but the limited convergence of β_{eff} sensitivity to scattering achievable in core simulations leaves an open question on this. In MOX systems, $^{238}\text{U}(n,f)$ is the most important contribution, followed by other ^{238}U data and by $\bar{\nu}_p$ and χ_p of ^{239}Pu . This can be explained by the harder spectrum found in the assembly model with respect to the full core. Scattering sensitivity convergence issues are found in this case as well for coolant materials.

Table I shows the different sensitivity of k_{eff} and β_{eff} to $\bar{\nu}_d$. While minimal changes of $u(k_{\text{eff}})$ are observed including a covariance for $\bar{\nu}_d$ in JEFF-3.3, the effect is relevant on $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$. Since the same sensitivity profiles were used to calculate $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$ with JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-3.3- ν_d , the two estimates of $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$ are largely correlated and the confidence intervals reported for $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$ should not be considered for their comparison. This highlights the need for covariance evaluations for $\bar{\nu}_d$, necessary for the study of uncertainties and correlations between systems, if β_{eff} is considered. The correlation between $\bar{\nu}_p$ and $\bar{\nu}_d$ could also play a role. When $\bar{\nu}_d$ is included in the uncertainty budget, it is the first or second contributor in all considered cases. Even with JEFF-3.3- ν_d , $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$ is likely underestimated, as suggested by the difference between the considered $\bar{\nu}_d$ uncertainty ($\approx 0.5\%$) and what is reported in other evaluations (e.g., ENDF/B-VIII.0 [18] $\approx 4.5\%$, which would make $\bar{\nu}_d$ the first contributor to $u(\beta_{\text{eff}})$).

3.2. Correlation with VENUS-F

The correlation of the considered designs to VENUS-F CC14 and VENUS-F MOX is presented in Table II. Auto-correlations are 100% by definition. As $u(k_{\text{eff}})$ is driven by the nuclear data of the fuel, rather large correlations are observed between the calculated k_{eff} of the considered systems. The larger similarity of CC14 to CC13 than to SNEAK 4A and CEFR is reflected by the k_{eff} correlation results: CC14 and CC13 are 100%-correlated, as they use the same fuel in a similar loading. The different coolant (simulator) of SNEAK 4A and CEFR than that of VENUS-F explains the lower correlation of CC14 to the sodium-systems. CEFR has the highest fuel enrichment and this reflects to a lower correlation with CC14. The impact of the covariance matrix of $\bar{\nu}_d$ is again negligible for k_{eff} and major for β_{eff} , as already observed in the propagated nuclear data uncertainties, where an increase in correlation is observed. For U systems, the analysis of the β_{eff} representativity is prevented by the limited convergence of scattering sensitivities: this results in the large uncertainties reported in Table II which lead to a lower correlation of CC14 to CC13 than to other reactors, which is not realistic. Despite its lower enrichment, the VENUS-F MOX assembly design proposed here emerges as a rather representative one, with correlations comparable to those observed between ^{235}U -fueled research reactors and VENUS-F CC14. The large similarity of ALFRED to VENUS-F MOX is reflected in Table II: it was shown that different enrichment results in different sensitivity to the nuclear data of ^{238}U and can hence lower the correlation [17].

The performance of the proposed VENUS-F 3D MOX assembly design makes us optimistic on the potential of a MOX loading in VENUS-F in terms of nuclear data studies in support of fast MOX-fueled reactor designs. The low correlation between the VENUS-F MOX assembly and VENUS-F CC13 ($k_{\text{eff}} : \approx 4\%$; $\beta_{\text{eff}} : \approx 20\%$) highlights that a VENUS-F MOX loading would open the door to new measurements, complementary of the past ones with respect to nuclear data feedback. It should be noted here that because of its relatively low enrichment and the limited fuel availability, the VENUS-F MOX assembly design introduced could not produce a fully MOX fueled critical VENUS-F core. Using a ^{235}U driver would reduce the correlation observed for the assembly: research is ongoing on this matter.

Table II. Nuclear data correlation of each case study to VENUS-F CC14 (^{235}U -fueled) or VENUS-F MOX (MOX-fueled).

	k_{eff} [%]		β_{eff} [%]	
	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3. ν_d	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-3.3. ν_d
VENUS-F CC14	100	100	100	100
VENUS-F CC13	100 ± 0.0	100 ± 0.0	77.3 ± 11	84.4 ± 10
SNEAK 4A	97.5 ± 0.1	97.5 ± 0.1	88.5 ± 7	91.6 ± 5
CEFR	96.5 ± 0.1	96.5 ± 0.1	91.0 ± 4	92.8 ± 2
VENUS-F MOX	100	100	100	100
MYRRHA (assembly)	94.8 ± 0.0	94.8 ± 0.0	94.2 ± 3	95.3 ± 2
ALFRED (assembly)	96.8 ± 0.0	96.8 ± 0.0	95.2 ± 1	96.4 ± 1

3.3. Transposition from ^{235}U systems to the k_{eff} of VENUS-F CC14

As discussed for equations 5-7, the transposition process consists of performing nuclear data assimilation on a benchmark (VENUS-F CC13, SNEAK 4A or CEFR, here) and transposing these results to an application (VENUS-F CC14, here). We consider the case of k_{eff} , which experimental value is 1 with a supposed experimental uncertainty of 10 pcm neglecting the experiment model uncertainty. CC14 was loaded [14] and the measured critical control rod height is included in its model. CC14 is then a suitable test case as we transpose from VENUS-F CC13, SNEAK 4A or CEFR to k'_{eff} having a target value of 1. Figure 2 shows values and uncertainties of the prior k_{eff} for the four case studies under analysis and of the posterior k'_{eff} transposed to VENUS-F CC14 from the other systems. With transposition, the uncer-

Figure 2. Prior (blue) and posterior (others) k_{eff} . Prior uncertainties truncated by the vertical axis are in Table I.

tainty reduction expected from equations 5 and 7 is clear, and all posterior k'_{eff} values lie within 1σ from the criticality ($k_{\text{eff}} = 1$). Because of the high correlation among systems (see Table II), the k_{eff} update is almost fully transferred to VENUS-F CC14, i.e., the larger the calculation to experiment discrepancy, the larger the (transposed) update. This reflects the fact that the nuclear data were assimilated just enough to make the calculation match the experiment for each case. Yet, the k'_{eff} values obtained transposing from the different systems are quite different: the information transposed from CEFR ($k_{\text{eff}} < 1$) moves k'_{eff} of VENUS-F CC14 upwards, while the other case studies do the opposite. Even if trans-

position should ideally be performed from an unbiased model (i.e., a model where all the calculation to experiment discrepancy originates from the nuclear data) as discussed in [1], this is hardly the case considering the simplifications required in full core and experiment simulations. Figure 2 also shows the impact of considering models with a similar calculation-to-experiment discrepancy (e.g.: VENUS-F CC13 and CC14): the posterior nuclear data would be adjusted to cover for such a discrepancy as well, even if it comes from a bias, which is non-physical. Yet, this results in a suit that performs astonishingly well for applications with high representativity and similar bias, if any, which is likely the case for updated versions of the same core. This seems to be a relevant limitation of the transposition framework: model bias identification and correction represents a major challenge because of the strong connection between any model and its input parameters (nuclear data in this case, with a very large uncertainty, that could in principle explain the whole calculation-to-experiment discrepancy). On the other hand, use of a non-zero model uncertainty to sum to the experimental one to account for this would reduce the information content transferable to the application, mostly increasing on the posterior uncertainty, but also partly affecting the transposed k_{eff} .

4. CONCLUSIONS

Nuclear data uncertainties were linearly propagated to k_{eff} and β_{eff} calculated with Serpent for seven case studies of fast systems. Four are research reactors fueled by U (VENUS-F CC13 and CC14, SNEAK-4A and CEFR) and three are assemblies fueled by MOX (MYRRHA, ALFRED, VENUS-F MOX assembly design.) Overall, fuel data are found to be the most relevant, with k_{eff} uncertainties around 1500 pcm for the full core models, while lower uncertainties around 950 pcm are calculated for the assembly models. The results for β_{eff} highlight the importance of $\bar{\nu}_d$ uncertainty evaluations, missing in JEFF-3.3: considering the evaluated covariance matrices for $\bar{\nu}_p$ in JEFF-3.3 for $\bar{\nu}_d$ as well, increases the uncertainty of β_{eff} by more than 15%.

The correlation of the considered U systems with VENUS-F CC14 coming from the use of the same nuclear data in their simulation was calculated. Very high ($> 96\%$) correlations are found for k_{eff} , while the slow sensitivity convergence prevents any conclusions on β_{eff} . Similarly, for the MOX cases the correlation to the proposed VENUS-F MOX assembly design is computed. The proposed design is found to perform very well (correlation $\gtrsim 95\%$). This result is quite encouraging towards a MOX loading of VENUS-F, even if the limited amount of fuel available and its enrichment ($\approx 14\%$) would require the inclusion of a U driver in VENUS-F, which effect on the presented correlations shall be assessed.

Transposition as an extension of nuclear data assimilation to a target application was performed for k_{eff} of the U systems, considering VENUS-F CC14 as a target design. Model biases lower than the propagated nuclear data uncertainties are hard to identify; yet they can strongly impact the results. Transposition from VENUS-F CC13 gives the best results because of the very similar calculation to experiment discrepancy in the two VENUS-F configurations. Any model bias present there would be incorporated in the posterior nuclear data resulting in nonphysical data that would work well for applications characterized by high representativity and similar calculation to experiment discrepancies. The adjustment brought by SNEAK-4A and CEFR to VENUS-F CC14 is rather limited because of the better agreement they show between calculations and experiments. Including model uncertainty mostly affects the posterior uncertainties, making them larger, yet it has a limited impact on the transposed k_{eff} as well. The impact of the assumptions behind the transposition approach (e.g.: linearity, energy grid for sensitivity scoring, need for sensitivity recalculation in the target system) is left for future works.

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